

List of OHEJP Publications 2020

The One Health EJP is a landmark partnership between partners across Europe, aligning and integrating medical, veterinary and environmental scientific communities to address potential and existing risks that originate at the animal-human-environmental interface.

All our project outcomes from the 5 year programme are available to view in yearly publication lists and via our [website](#).

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Molecular characterisation and antimicrobial susceptibility of *C. jejuni* isolates from Italian wild bird populations

Marotta, F., Janowicz, A., Di Marcantonio, L., Ercole, C., Di Donato, G., Garofolo, G., Di Giannatale, E., (2020). *Pathogens*. 9(4), 304.

Project: **AIRSAMPLE**

Isolation, Genotyping, and Mouse Virulence Characterisation of *Toxoplasma gondii* From Free Ranging Iberian Pigs

Fernández-Escobar, M., Calero-Bernal, R., Regidor-Cerrillo, J., Vallejo, R., Benavides, J., Collantes-Fernández, E., Ortega-Mora, LM. (2020). *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*. 7:604782.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Genetic Characterisation of a *Listeria monocytogenes* Serotype IV b Variant 1 Strain Isolated from Vegetal Matrix in Italy

Torresi, M., Orsini, M., Acciari, V., Centorotola, G., Di Lollo, V., Di Domenico, M, Manila Bianchi, D., Wakwamba Ziba, M., Tramuta, C., Cammà, C., Pomilio, F. (2020). *Microbiology Resource Announcements*. 9:e00782-20.

Project: **LISTADAPT**

Population genomics and antimicrobial resistance in *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*

Hennart, M., Panunzi, LG., Rodrigues, C., Gaday, Q., Baines, SL., Barros-Pinkelnic, M., Carmi-Leroy, A., Dazas, M., Wehenkel, AM., Didelot, X., Toubiana, J., Badell, E., Brisse, S. (2020). *Genome Medicine*. 12, p 1-18.

Project: **Codes4strains (PhD)**

Rapid SARS-CoV-2 whole-genome sequencing and analysis for informed public health decision-making in the Netherlands

Oude Munnink, BB., Nieuwenhuijse, DF., Stein, M., O'Toole, A., Haverkate, M., Mollers, M., Kamga, SK., Schapendonk, C., Pronk, M., Lexmond, P., van der Linden, A., Bestebroer, T., Chestakova, I., Overmars, RJ., van Nieuwkoop, S., Molenkamp, R., van der Eijk, AA., Geurtsvan Kessel, C., Vennema, H., Meijer, A., Rambaut, A., van Dissel, J., Sikkema, RS., Timen, A., Koopmans, M. (2020). *Nature Medicine*. 26, p 1405-1410.

Project: **METASTAVA**

Mobile colistin resistance gene *mcr-1* detected on an IncI1 plasmid in *Escherichia coli* from meat

Brouwer, MSM., Goodman, RN., Kant, A., Mevius, D., Newire, E., Roberts, AP., Veldman, KT. (2020). *Journal of Global Antimicrobial Resistance*. 23, 145-148.

Project: **ARDIG**

Identification of a *bla*_{VIM-1}-Carrying IncA/C₂ Multiresistance Plasmid in an *Escherichia coli* Isolate Recovered from the German Food Chain

Pauly, N., Hammerl, JA., Grobbel, M., Käsbohrer, A., Tenhagen, BA., Malorny, B., Schwarz, S., Meemken, D., Irrgang, A. (2020). *Microorganisms*. 9, 29.

Project: **IMPART**

Diversity of mucoid to non-mucoid switch among carbapenemase-producing *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

Chiarelli, A., Cabanel, N., Rosinski-Chupin, I., Zongo PD., Naas. T., Bonnin, RA., Glaser, P. (2020). *BMC Microbiology*, 20, 325.

Project: **MedVetKlebs**

The importance of using whole genome sequencing and extended spectrum beta-lactamase selective media when monitoring antimicrobial resistance

Duggett, N., AbuOun, M., Randall, L., Horton, R., Lemma, F., Rogers, J., Crook, D., Teale, C., Anjum, MF. (2020). *Scientific Reports*. 10, 19880.

Project: **ARDIG**

Temporal dynamics of the fecal microbiota in veal calves in a 6-month field trial

Massot, M., Haenni, M., Nguyen, TT., Madec, JY., Mentré, F., Denamur, E. (2020). *Animal Microbiome*. 2(32).

Project: **ARDIG**

Modelling spread and surveillance of *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *paratuberculosis* in the Swedish cattle trade network

Rosendal, T., Widgren, S., Ståhl, K., Frössling, J. (2020). *Preventative Veterinary Medicine*. 183, 105152.

Project: **NOVA**

Novel IncFII plasmid harbouring *bla*_{NDM-4} in a carbapenem-resistant *Escherichia coli* of pig origin, Italy

Diaconu, EL., Carfora, V., Alba, P., Di Matteo, P., Stravino, F., Buccella, C., Dell'Aira, E., Onorati, R., Sorbara, L., Battisti, A., Franco, A. (2020). *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*. 75(12), 3475–3479.

Project: **IMPART** and **FULLFORCE**

First Detection of GES-5-Producing *Escherichia coli* from Livestock—An Increasing Diversity of Carbapenemases Recognized from German Pig Production

Irrgang, A., Tausch SH., Pauly, N., Grobbel, M., Kaesbohrer, A., Hammerl, JA. (2020). *Microorganisms*. 8 (10), 159.

Project: **IMPART**

ChromID® CARBA Agar Fails to Detect Carbapenem-Resistant *Enterobacteriaceae* With Slightly Reduced Susceptibility to Carbapenems

Pauly, N., Hammerl, JA., Grobbel, M., Tenhagen, BA., Käsbohrer, A., Bisenius, S., Fuchs, J., Horlacher, S., Lingstädt, H., Mauermann, U., Mitro, S., Müller, M., Rohrmann, S., Schiffmann, AP., Stührenberg, B., Zimmermann, P., Schwarz, S., Meemken, D., Irrgang, A. (2020). *Frontiers in Microbiology*. 11, 1678.

Project: **IMPART**

Spill-Over from Public Health? First Detection of an OXA-48-Producing *Escherichia coli* in a German Pig Farm

Irrgang, A., Pauly, N., Tenhagen, BA., Grobbel, M., Kaesbohrer, A., Hammerl, JA. (2020). *Microorganisms*. 8(6), 855.

Project: **IMPART**

Comparison of Two DNA Extraction Methods and Two PCRs for Detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in the Stool Samples of Naturally Infected Red Foxes

Skrzypek, K., Karamon, J., Samorek-Pieróg, M., Dąbrowska, J., Kochanowski, M., Sroka, J., Bilska-Zajac, E., Cencek Tomasz. (2020). *Animals*. 10, 2381.

Project: **MeME**

The state of One Health research across disciplines and sectors – a bibliometric analysis

Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden, S., Olivier, R., Frid-Nielsen, SS. (2020). *One Health*, 10, pp. 100146.

Project: **SUSTAIN (PhD)**

Using stochastic dynamic modelling to estimate the sensitivity of current and alternative surveillance program of *Salmonella* in conventional broiler production

Apenteng, OO., Arnold, ME., Vigre, H. (2020). *Scientific Reports*, 10, pp. 19441.

Project: **NOVA**

Whole-Genome Sequencing to Detect Numerous *Campylobacter jejuni* Outbreaks and Match Patient Isolates to Sources, Denmark, 2015–2017

Joensen, KG., Kiil, K., Gantzhorn, MR., Nauerby, B., Engberg, J., Holt, HM., Nielsen, HL., Petersen, AM., Kuhn, KG., Sandø, G., Ethelberg, S., Nielsen, EM. (2020). *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, 26(3), 523-532.

Project: **ORION**

Novel enteric viruses in fatal enteritis of grey squirrels

Dastjerdi, A., Benfield, C., Everest, D., Stidworthy, MF., Zell, R. (2020). *Journal of General Virology*, 101, pp. 746–75.

Project: **MADVir**

An alternative workflow for molecular detection of SARS-CoV-2 – escape from the NA extraction kit-shortage, Copenhagen, Denmark, March 2020

Fomsgaard, AS., Rosenstjerne, MW. (2020). *Eurosurveillance*. 25(14), pp: 2000398.

Project: **TELE-Vir**

Cost-effectiveness analysis of using probiotics, prebiotics, or synbiotics to control *Campylobacter* in broilers

van Wagenberg, CPA., van Horne, P.L.M., van Asseldonk, M.A.P.M. (2020). *Poultry Science*. 99 (8), pp. 4077- 4084.

Project: **MOMIR**

Climatic and topographic tolerance limits of wild boar in Eurasia: implications for their expansion

Bosch, J., Iglesias, I., Martínez, M., de la Torre, A. (2020). *Geography, Environment, Sustainability*, 13(1), pp.107-114.

Project: **NOVA**

A Multi-Scale Epidemic Model of *Salmonella* infection with Heterogeneous Shedding

Hoorfar, J., Kolářčková, I., Johannessen, GS., Garofolo, G., Marotta, F., Wiczorek, K., Osek, J., Labarthe, S., Laroche, B., Nguyen, T. N. T., Polizzi, B., Patout, F., Ribot, M., Stegmaier, T. (2020). *ESAIM: Proceedings and Surveys*, 67, p. 261-284.

Project: **MOMIR**

A multi-center proposal for a fast screening tool in biosecured chicken flocks. Foodborne *Campylobacter*

Hoorfar, J., Kolářčková, I., Johannessen, GS., Garofolo, G., Marotta, F., Wiczorek, K., Osek, J., Torp, M., Spilsberg, B., Sekse, C., Thornval, NR., Karpíšková, R. (2020). *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 86 (20) e01051-20.

Project: **AIRSAMPLE**

Extensive antimicrobial resistance mobilization via multicopy plasmid encapsidation mediated by temperate phages

Rodriguez-Rubio, L., Serna, C., Ares-Arroyo, M., Matamoros, BR., Delgado-Blas, JF., Montero, N., Bernabe-Balas, C., Wedel, EF., Mendez, IS., Muniesa, M., Gonzalez-Zorn, B. (2020). *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*, 75 (11), pp. 3173–3180.

Project: **ARDIG**

First report on the occurrence of *Listeria monocytogenes* ST121 strain in a dolphin brain
Sévellec, Y., Torresi, M., Félix, B., Palma, F., Centorotola, G., Bilei, S., Senese, M., Terracciano, G., Leblanc, J.C., Pomilio, F., Roussel, S. (2020). *Pathogens*. 9 (10), 802.

Project: **LISTADAPT**

Cystic Echinococcosis: Clinical, Immunological, and Biomolecular Evaluation of Patients from Sardinia (Italy)

Santucci, C., Bonelli, P., Peruzzu, A., Fancellu, A., Marras, V., Carta, A., Mastrandrea, S., Bagella, G., Piseddu, T., Profili, S., Porcu, A., Masala, G. (2020). *Pathogens*. 9 (11), 907.

Project: **MeME**

Expression of *in vivo* biotinylated recombinant antigens SAG1 and SAG2A from *Toxoplasma gondii* for improved seroepidemiological bead-based multiplex assays

Santolamazza, F., Santoro, A., Possenti, A., Cacciò, S M., Casulli, A. (2020). *Infection, Genetics and Evolution*. 85, 104575.

Project: **MeME**

Reduction of *Salmonella* Typhimurium cecal colonisation and improvement of intestinal health in broilers supplemented with fermented defatted 'alperujo', an olive oil by-product

Rebollada-Merino, A., Ugarte-Ruiz, M., Hernández, M., Miguela-Villoldo, P., Abad, D., Rodríguez-Lázaro, D., de Juan, L., Domínguez, L., Rodríguez-Bertos, A. (2020). *Animals*. 10 (10), 1931.

Project: **MOMIR**

A validated method to identify *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* at species level

Santolamazza, F., Santoro, A., Possenti, A., Cacciò, S M., Casulli, A. (2020). *Infection, Genetics and Evolution*. 85, 104575.

Project: **MeME**

Bayesian Analysis of Three Methods for Diagnosis of Cystic Echinococcosis in Sheep

Bonelli, P., Loi, F., Cancedda, M.G., Peruzzu, A., Antuofermo, E., Pintore, E., Piseddu, T., Garippa, G., Masalam G. (2020). *Pathogens*. 9(10), 796.

Project: **MeME**

Species Detection within the *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* Complex by Novel Probe-Based Real-Time PCRs

Maksimov, P., Bergmann, H., Wassermann, M., Romig, T., Gottstein, B., Casulli, A., Conraths, F.J. (2020). *Pathogens*, 9(10), 791.

Project: **MeME**

Dietary supplementation with fermented defatted "alperujo" induces modifications of the intestinal mucosa and cecal microbiota of broiler chickens

Rebollada-Merino, A., Ugarte-Ruiz, M., Hernández, M., Miguela-Villoldo, P., Abad, D., Cuesta-Álvaro, P., Rodríguez-Lázaro, D., de Juan, L., Domínguez, L., Rodríguez-Bertos, A. (2020). *Poultry Science*.

Project: **MOMIR**

Gut microbiota composition before infection determines the *Salmonella* super- and low-shedder phenotypes in chicken

Helmuth, I.G., Espenhain, L., Ethelberg, S., Jensen, T., Kjeldgaard, J., Litrup, E., Schjørring, S., Müller, L. (2019). *Epidemiology and Infection*, 147, pp. e315.

Project: **MOMIR**

Isolation and genetic characterization of *Toxoplasma gondii* in Spanish sheep flocks

Fernández-Escobar, M., Calero-Bernal, R., Benavides, J., Regidor-Cerrillo, J., Guerrero-Molina, M. C., Gutiérrez-Expósito, D., Collantes-Fernández, E., Ortega-Mora, L. M. (2020). *Parasites and Vectors*.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Fluorescent bead-based serological detection of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection in chickens

Gay, E., Bour, M., Cazeau, G., Jarrige, N., Martineau, C., Madec, JY., Haenni, M. (2019). *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 10, pp. 792.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Veterinary Students Have A Higher Risk Of Contracting Cryptosporidiosis When Calves With High Fecal *Cryptosporidium* Loads Are Used For Fetotomy Exercises

Lopez, T., Müller, L., Vestergaard, LS., Christoffersen, M., Andersen, A., Jokelainen, P., Agerholm, JS., Stensvold, CR. (2020). *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*.

Project: **PARADISE**

The One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP), 2018–2022: an exemplary One Health initiative

Brown, HL., Passey, JL., Getino, M., Pursley, I., Basu, P., Horton, DL., La Ragione, RM. (2020). *Journal of Medical Microbiology*, pp 1-3.

MLST-based genetic relatedness of *Campylobacter jejuni* isolated from chickens and humans in Poland

Wieczorek, K., Wołkowicz, T., Osek, J. (2020). *PLOS ONE*, 15(1), e0226238

Project: **AIRSAMPLE**

Effects on Intestinal Mucosal Morphology, Productive Parameters and Microbiota Composition after Supplementation with Fermented Defatted Alperujo (FDA) in Laying Hens

Rebollada-Merino A., Bárcena C., Ugarte-Ruiz M., Porrás-González N., Mayoral-Alegre F., Tome-Sánchez I., Domínguez L. and Rodríguez-Bertos A. (2020). *Antibiotics*, 8(4), pp. 215

Project: **MedVetKlebs**

Broad-Spectrum Cephalosporin-Resistant *Klebsiella spp.* Isolated from Diseased Horses in Austria

Loncaric, I., Rosel, AC., Szostak, MP., Licka, TF., Allerberger, F., Ruppitsch, W., Spargser, J. (2020). *Animals*, 10(2), pp. 332

Project: **MedVetKlebs**

***Campylobacter* in chicken- Critical parameters for international, multi-centre evaluation of air sampling and detection method**

Johannessen, GS., Giuliano Garofolo, G., Di Serafino, G., Koláčková, I., Karpíšková, R., Wieczorek, K., Osek, J., Christensen, J., Torp, M., Hoorfar, J. (2020). *Food Microbiology*, 90, 1-6

Project: **AIRSAMPLE**

Evaluation of a commercial exogenous internal process control for diagnostic RNA virus metagenomics from different animal clinical samples

Van Borm, S., Fu, Q., Winand, R., Vanneste, K., Hakhverdyan, M., Höper, D., Vandenbussche, F. (2020). *Journal of Virological Methods*, 283

Project: **METASTAVA**

***Klebsiella pneumoniae* carriage in low-income countries: antimicrobial resistance, genomic diversity and risk factors**

Huynh, BT., Passet, V., Rakotondrasoa, A., Diallo, T., Kerleguer, A., Hennart, M., Lauzanne, A., Herindrainy, P., Seck, A., Bercion, R., Borand, L., Pardos de la Gandara, M., Delarocque-Astagneau, E., Guillemot, D., Vray, M., Garin, B., Collard, JM., Rodrigues, C., Brisse, S. (2020). *Gut Microbes*, 11(5), pp. 1287-1299.

Project: **MedVetKlebs**

The ZKIR Assay, a Real-Time PCR Method for the Detection of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and Closely Related Species in Environmental Samples

Barbier, E., Rodrigues, C., Depret, G., Passet, V., Gal, L., Piveteau, P., Brisse, S. (2020). *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 86(7), pp. e02711-19.

Project: **MedVetKlebs**

Stepwise evolution and convergent recombination underlie the global dissemination of carbapenemase-producing *Escherichia coli*

Patiño-Navarrete, R., Rosinski-Chupin, I., Cabanel, N., Gauthier, L., Takissian, J., Madec, JY., Hamze, M., Bonnin, RA., Naas, T., Glaser, P. (2020). *Genome Medicine*, 12(10).

Project: **ARDIG**

Microsatellite Investigations of Multiple *Echinococcus granulosus* Sensu Stricto Cysts in Single Hosts Reveal Different Patterns of Infection Events between Livestock and Humans

M'rad, S., Oudni-M'rad, M., Bastid, V., Bournez, L., Mosbahi, S., Nouri, A., Babba, H., Grenouillet, F., Boué, F., Umhang, G. (2020). *Pathogens*, 9(6), pp. 444.

Project: **MeME**

Analysis of COMPASS, a New Comprehensive Plasmid Database Revealed Prevalence of Multireplicon and Extensive Diversity of IncF Plasmids

Douarre, P E., Mallet, L., Radomski, N., Felten, A., Mistou, M. (2020) *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 11, pp. 1-15.

Project: **RaDAR**

Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemics cystic and alveolar echinococcosis

Casulli, A. (2020) *The Lancet*, 8 (4): PE470-E471.

Project: **MeME**

All OHEJP Publications from the 5 year programme can be viewed at: onehealthejp.eu